

ASSESSMENT OF RELATIVE SUSCEPTIBILITY OF BRINJAL VARIETIES/GENOTYPES TO SHOOT AND FRUIT BORER UNDER FIELD CONDITIONS

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Abstract

The experiment was carried out during two consecutive years 2021-22 and 2022-23 at Regional Horticultural Research Station, Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari to assess brinjal varieties/ genotypes for their relative susceptibility against shoot and fruit borer under field condition, *Lucinodes orbonalis* Guenee during Rabi season on brinjal. The results revealed considerable variation in shoot damage among the tested genotypes. GNRB-1 recorded the highest shoot damage (13.43%), followed by GRB-5 (12.49%), GJB-3 (12.09%), and NBL-50 (11.22%). In contrast, NBL-117 was categorized as highly resistant, while Swarna Mani, Surati Raviya, GOB-1, and GAOB-2 exhibited resistance. Genotypes such as NBL-50 and GJB-2 were found to be susceptible, whereas GJB-3 and GRB-5 showed moderate susceptibility. The classification of GNRB-1 as highly susceptible highlights the substantial genotypic variation in response to shoot and fruit borer infestation under field conditions.

Key words: Brinjal genotypes, Shoot and fruit borer, *Lucinodes orbonalis*, Resistance, Field evaluation

Introduction

Brinjal (*Solanum melongena* L.), an important member of the Solanaceae family, plays a significant role in crop diversification and contributes to nutritional and economic security in India. It ranks as the fourth most important vegetable crop in the country, following potato, onion, and tomato. Grown across a wide range of agro-climatic regions, brinjal serves as a staple vegetable, often referred to as the "poor man's vegetable" due to its affordability and widespread consumption. India is the second-largest producer of brinjal globally, with major cultivation in states like Gujarat, West Bengal, and Maharashtra. Brinjal is highly nutritious and valued for its medicinal properties, making it a common ingredient in various culinary preparations. Despite its significance, brinjal cultivation faces serious challenges from biotic stresses, particularly the brinjal shoot and fruit borer (*Leucinodes orbonalis* Guenee), a major pest causing severe damage throughout the crop's lifecycle. Infestations by this pest can lead to yield losses of up to 92%, significantly affecting both productivity and fruit quality. The use of host plant resistance, governed by morphological and biochemical plant traits, has shown promise as part of integrated pest management strategies. In this context, the present study aims to explore the resistance mechanisms against *L. orbonalis* under the agro-climatic conditions of South Gujarat.

Material and method

An experiment was carried out at the Regional Horticultural Research Station, Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari, during two consecutive years (2021–22 and 2022–23) to evaluate different varieties/genotypes of brinjal for their relative susceptibility to shoot and fruit borer under field conditions. The tested varieties were maintained without any insecticidal sprays throughout the crop period, while all other recommended agronomic practices were followed to ensure proper crop growth.

Methods of recording observation

For this purpose, 5 plants were randomly selected and tagged from net plot area and the incidence of brinjal shoot and fruit borer was recorded based on number of infected shoots as well as fruits. The observations were recorded during early morning hours at weekly interval. The shoot damage was recorded from tagged plants by counting the total and damaged shoots per plant at weekly interval and data were recorded starting from one week after transplanting. In case of fruit infestation, the fruits of five tagged plants were carefully examined for damage of shoot and fruit borer. The fruit damage was recorded by counting the total and damaged fruits per plant on number and weight basis of fruits at the time of each picking.

$$\text{per cent shoot damage (No. basis)} = \frac{\text{Total number of damage shoots}}{\text{Total number of shoots}} \times 100$$

Categories of varieties/ genotypes

The brinjal varieties/ genotypes were also grouped in the four categories of resistance to brinjal shoot and fruit borer viz., highly resistant, resistant, susceptible and highly susceptible based on brinjal shoot and fruit borer population. For the purpose, mean value of

individual varieties (X_i) was compared with mean value of all varieties (\bar{X}) and standard deviation (SD) following the modified scale adopted by Patel *et al.* (2002). The retransformed data were used for computation of \bar{X} , X_i and SD in case of this parameter. The scale used for categorizing different varieties was as under.

Categories of Resistance	Scale for Resistance
Highly resistance	$\bar{X}_i < (\bar{X} - SD)$
Resistance	$\bar{X}_i > (\bar{X} - SD) < (\bar{X} - 0.5 SD)$
Susceptible	$\bar{X}_i > (\bar{X} - 0.5 SD) < (\bar{X} + 0.5 SD)$
Moderately susceptible	$\bar{X}_i > (\bar{X} + 0.5 SD) < (\bar{X} + 1.5 SD)$
Highly susceptible	$\bar{X}_i > (\bar{X} + 1.5 SD)$

Result and Discussion**1. Shoot damage**

The results presented in Table 1 and illustrated in Fig. 1 on the percentage of shoot damage caused by *Leucinodes orbonalis* across different genotypes/varieties revealed a significant variation during both the individual years and in the pooled analysis. The shoot damage

ranged from 8.53% to 14.31% in 2021–22, 8.17% to 12.55% in 2022–23, and 8.94% to 13.43% in the pooled data.

Shoot damage First year (2021-22)

A significant variation in shoot damage was observed among the different brinjal genotypes/varieties. The highest shoot damage was recorded in genotype GNRB-1 (14.31%), followed by GRB-5

(13.51%), GJB-3 (12.65%), and NBL-50 (11.67%). Moderate levels of shoot damage were observed in GAOB-2 (10.68%) and Surati Ravaiya (10.53%). In contrast, lower damage levels were recorded in GJB-2 (9.80%), GOB-1 (9.52%), and NBL-117 (8.87%), with the lowest being in the variety Swarna Mani (8.53%). These results, as presented in Table 1 and Fig. 1, highlight the differential susceptibility of brinjal genotypes to shoot borer infestation.

Shoot damage Second year (2022-23)

A significant variation in shoot damage was recorded among the different brinjal genotypes/varieties. The highest shoot damage was

observed in GNRB-1 (12.55%), followed by GJB-3 (11.52%), GRB-5 (11.47%), and NBL-50 (10.76%). Moderate levels of damage were noted in GJB-2 (9.72%), Swarna Mani (9.36%), and GOB-1 (9.27%). Among the genotypes with relatively low shoot damage, NBL-117 (8.36%) performed better, while the lowest damage was recorded in GAOB-2 (8.17%). The variety Surati Ravaiya (8.21%) showed shoot damage that was statistically at par with GAOB-2. These findings, as summarized in Table 1 and illustrated in Fig. 1, reflect the differential susceptibility of the tested genotypes to shoot borer infestation.

Table 1: Per cent shoot damage by *L. orbonalis* observed in different brinjal genotypes/ varieties

Genotype/ varieties	Shoot damage (%)	Shoot damage (%)	Shoot damage (%)
	2021-22	2022-23	2021-22 and 2022-23
	Mean	Mean	Pooled
T1 Surati Ravaiya	1.95 (10.53)	1.74 (8.21)	1.84 (9.37)
T2 GAOB-2	1.96 (10.68)	1.73 (8.17)	1.85 (9.42)
T3 GRB-5	2.18 (13.51)	2.02 (11.47)	2.1 (12.49)
T4 Swarna Mani	1.77 (8.53)	1.84 (9.36)	1.81 (8.94)
T5 NBL-50	2.04 (11.67)	1.97 (10.76)	2.00 (11.22)
T6 GJB-3	2.12 (12.65)	2.03 (11.52)	2.07 (12.09)
T7 GJB-2	1.88 (9.80)	1.88 (9.72)	1.88 (9.76)
T8 GOB-1	1.86 (9.52)	1.84 (9.27)	1.85 (9.40)
T9 GNRB-1	2.24 (14.31)	2.11 (12.55)	2.18 (13.43)
T10 NBL-117	1.8 (8.87)	1.75 (8.36)	1.78 (8.61)
SEm± (T)	0.02	0.03	0.02
CD at 5 % (T)	0.06	0.09	0.05
SEm± (Y X T)	-	-	0.03
CD at 5 % (Y X T)	-	-	0.07
CV (%)	1.71	2.75	2.30

Note: Figure in parentheses are retransformed values, those outside are arc sign transformed value

Shoot damage Pooled (2021-22 and 2022-23)

A significant difference in shoot damage was observed among the genotypes, as shown in Table 4.1 and Fig. 4.1. The lowest percentage of shoot damage was recorded in the variety NBL-117 (8.61%), while the highest was noted in the genotype GNRB-1 (13.43%). GNRB-1 was followed by GRB-5 (12.49%), GJB-3 (12.09%), and NBL-50 (11.22%). Moderate levels of damage were observed in GJB-2 (9.76%), GAOB-2 (9.42%), GOB-1 (9.40%), and Surati Ravaiya (9.37%), whereas Swarna Mani (8.94%) and NBL-117 (8.61%) recorded the lowest levels of shoot damage.

Overall, it can be concluded from Table 1 and Fig. 1 that NBL-117 and Swarna Mani exhibited the lowest shoot damage, while GNRB-1

recorded the highest damage, indicating greater susceptibility to *L. orbonalis*.

Several researchers have previously screened brinjal genotypes/varieties for their susceptibility to *L. orbonalis*. Samota and Jat (2017) reported that Pusa Uttam, Ravaiya, and Kavach were less susceptible, with shoot damage below 18.61%. Similarly, Dahatonde *et al.* (2019) recorded the lowest shoot damage (2.26%) in genotype JBGL-10/20. However, direct comparison of the present results with those studies is limited, as the local genotypes/varieties evaluated in this investigation have not been previously assessed elsewhere.

4.1.1.3 Pooled data (2021-22 and 2022-23)

Fig 1: Per cent shoot damage by *L. orbonalis* observed in different brinja genotypes/ varieties

Table 2.: Categories of different genotypes/ varieties against *L. orbonalis* infesting brinjal with two infestation paramaters

Category of resistance	Scale	Genotype
1	2	3
Based on per cent shoot damage $\bar{X} = 10.47$, $SD = 1.69$		
Highly resistant	$\bar{X}_i < 8.78$	NBL-117 (8.61)
Resistant	$\bar{X}_i > 8.78 < 9.63$	Swarna Mani (8.94) Surati Raviya (9.37) GOB-1 (9.40) GAOB-2 (9.42)
Susceptible	$\bar{X}_i > 9.63 < 11.32$	GJB-2 (9.76) NBL-50 (11.22)
Moderately Susceptible	$\bar{X}_i > 11.32 < 13.01$	GJB-3 (12.09) GRB-5 (12.49)
Highly susceptible	$\bar{X}_i > 13.01$	GNRB-1 (13.43)

Based on the percentage of shoot damage caused by *L. orbonalis* infestation (as presented in Table 2), genotype NBL-117 was classified as highly resistant, with shoot damage below 8.78%. Genotypes such as Swarna Mani, Surati Raviya, GOB-1, and GAOB-2, which recorded shoot damage between 8.78% and 9.63%, were categorized as resistant. GJB-2 and NBL-50, showing damage between 9.63% and 11.32%, were considered susceptible. GJB-3 and GRB-5, with shoot damage ranging from 11.32% to 13.01%, were moderately susceptible. GNRB-1 exhibited the highest level of shoot damage, exceeding 13.01%, and was therefore classified as highly susceptible.

Overall, genotype NBL-117 was classified as highly resistant to shoot damage, followed by Swarna Mani, Surati Raviya, GOB-1, and GAOB-2, which exhibited resistance. In contrast, NBL-50 and GJB-2 were categorized as susceptible, while GJB-3 and GRB-5 showed moderate susceptibility. Notably, GNRB-1 was identified as highly susceptible to shoot damage, underscoring the significant variation in resistance levels among the evaluated genotypes.

In previous studies, Elanchezhayan *et al.* (2008) found that hybrids Ravaiya and Sweta were resistant to *L. orbonalis*. Dar and Mir (2016) evaluated Shalimar Brinjal and found Shalimar Brinjal Purple Round-

8 and Purple Round-1 to be resistant with regard to fruit infestation. Samota and Jat (2017) noted that Pusa Purple Round and Raunak were highly susceptible, while Pusa Uttam, Ravaiya, and Kavach showed less susceptibility. The results from the current study differ from these findings, possibly due to the use of different locations and genotypes in the respective studies.

Conclusion

The evaluation of diverse brinjal genotypes for resistance to *Leucinodes orbonalis* revealed significant variability in their susceptibility to shoot and fruit borer infestation. Among the genotypes assessed, NBL-117 exhibited the highest level of resistance, with minimal shoot damage (<8.78%), making it a promising candidate for cultivation in borer-prone regions. In contrast, GNRB-1 recorded the highest shoot (13.43%) damage, categorizing it as highly susceptible. Despite its vulnerability, the agronomic traits of GNRB-1 suggest its potential utility in breeding programs aimed at improving resistance while retaining desirable yield characteristics. These findings emphasize the importance of integrating host plant resistance into

integrated pest management strategies to enhance brinjal productivity and sustainability.

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